

p-Phenylenedibiguanide, which, like its *m*-phenylene analogue (cf. Rây and Siddhanta, *ibid.*, 1943, 20, 200; Rây and Das Sarma, *ibid.*, 1949, 26, 187), behaves as a quadridentate molecule, has been found to give as usual 4-coordinated copper and nickel complexes and only 6-coordinated dichromium tris-*p*-phenylenedibiguanide base. In this respect it differs from its *meta* isomer. The configuration of the 4- and 6-coordinated metallic complexes of this *para* derivative are represented below.

$C_6H_4(BigH_2)_2$ = a molecule of *p*-phenylenedibiguanide.

EXPERIMENTAL

p-Acetylamino phenylbiguanide Sulphate.—*p*-Aminoacetanilide (15g. in 80 c.c. water), dicyandiamide (8.4 g.) and 110 c.c. of 32% HCl were heated together under reflux for half an hour. The hot, coloured solution was treated with 5 g. of animal charcoal and filtered. The filtrate was treated with a saturated solution of ammonium sulphate and rendered strongly acid with sulphuric acid. The sulphate of the biguanide base crystallised out from the solution. The crystals were purified by dissolving them in dilute ammonia, treating the hot solution with charcoal, and then acidifying the filtrate with sulphuric acid. For further purification, the product was dissolved in water and treated with ammoniacal copper sulphate solution. The complex copper acetylamino biguanide sulphate was then decomposed with a moderately strong solution of sulphuric acid. The crystalline precipitate was washed free from copper sulphate and dissolved in caustic soda solution. On acidification with dilute sulphuric acid the pure *p*-acetylamino phenylbiguanide sulphate separated out. The crystalline product was filtered, washed first with water, then with alcohol, and finally dried in air. The substance is

sparingly soluble in water and reacts acidic to litmus. (Found: N, 24.67; SO_4 , 28.16. $\text{C}_{10}\text{N}_6\text{OH}_{11}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4\cdot 0.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 24.63; SO_4 , 28.15 per cent).

Copper bis-p-Acetylamino-phenylbiguanide.—When a solution of *p*-acetylamino-phenylbiguanide sulphate in dilute ammonia was treated with an ammoniacal solution of copper sulphate, the sulphate of the copper complex was precipitated. This was filtered and thoroughly washed. From this complex sulphate the corresponding base was obtained by treatment with an excess of caustic soda solution. The orange coloured base was washed with water till free from sulphate. The product was dried in a desiccator over solid KOH.

The orange coloured base is somewhat soluble in water, but insoluble in alcohol. Its solution reacts alkaline to litmus and liberates ammonia from ammonium salts, m.p. 206° with decomposition. {Found: Cu, 11.69; N, 31.11; H_2O (by loss at 110°), 1.66. $[\text{Cu}(\text{C}_{10}\text{N}_6\text{OH}_{11})_2] \cdot 0.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Cu, 11.79; N, 31.19; H_2O , 1.67 per cent}. [Found (for the dried product): Cu, 11.89; N, 31.70. Calc. Cu, 11.97; N, 31.70 per cent].

The Complex Chloride.—The above described complex copper base was digested, while still moist, with an excess of ammonium chloride solution on the water-bath till the evolution of ammonia ceased. The product was filtered and dissolved in water; and from the violet solution the complex chloride was precipitated by the addition of ammonium chloride. This was filtered, washed first with a little ice-cold water, then with alcohol, and finally dried in air.

The substance forms light violet crystals, soluble in water, m.p. 204° (decomp.). It also decomposes on boiling with water, giving a colloidal solution. {Found: Cu, 9.44; N, 25.03; Cl, 10.55; H_2O (by loss at 110°), 10.65. $[\text{Cu}(\text{C}_{10}\text{N}_6\text{H}_{11}\text{O})_2] \text{Cl}_{1.4}\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Cu, 9.41; N, 25.05; Cl, 10.55; H_2O , 10.67 per cent}. {Found (for the dried product): Cu, 10.50; N, 27.78. Calc. Cu, 10.53; N, 27.88 per cent.}

The *complex sulphate* was precipitated by adding an ammoniacal solution of copper sulphate to an ammoniacal solution of *p*-acetylamino-phenylbiguanide sulphate. The rose-red precipitate was washed with water and dried in air. It is sparingly soluble in water, insoluble in alcohol, but soluble in hot dilute ammonia. {Found: Cu, 9.08; N, 23.93; S, 13.77; H_2O (by loss at 110°), 10.28. $[\text{Cu}(\text{C}_{10}\text{N}_6\text{H}_{11}\text{O})_2] \text{SO}_{4.4}\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Cu, 9.08; N, 24.03; SO_4 , 13.72; H_2O , 10.29 per cent}. [Found (for the dried product): Cu, 10.10; N, 26.77. Calc. Cu, 10.11; N, 26.77 per cent].

Nickel bis-p-acetylamino-phenylbiguanide sulphate was prepared by adding a solution of nickel sulphate to an ammoniacal solution of *p*-acetylamino-phenylbiguanide sulphate. The brown precipitate was filtered, washed first with water, then with alcohol, and finally dried in air. The substance is sparingly soluble in water. {Found: Ni, 8.60; N, 24.98; S, 14.16; H_2O (by loss at 110°), 7.99. $[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_{10}\text{N}_6\text{H}_{11}\text{O})_2] \text{SO}_{4.3}\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Ni, 8.67; N, 24.83; S, 14.18; H_2O , 7.99 per cent}. [Found (for the dried product): Ni, 9.46; N, 27.19. Calc. Ni, 9.42; N, 27.01 per cent].

The *complex base* was obtained as a yellow product when the complex sulphate was triturated with an excess of alkali solution in a mortar. This was filtered, washed with water free from sulphate and then dried in a desiccator over solid KOH.

The substance is sparingly soluble in water and alcohol. Its solution is alkaline to litmus. It melts 248° with decomposition. It liberates ammonia from ammonium salt solution. {Found: Ni, 10.44; N, 29.95; H_2O (by loss at 105°), 6.41. $[Ni(C_{10}N_6H_{12}O)_2]$, $2H_2O$ requires Ni, 10.47; N, 29.96; H_2O , 6.42 per cent}. [Found (for the dried product): Ni, 11.20; N, 31.98. Calc. Ni, 11.18; N, 31.98 per cent].

The Complex Chloride.—The complex base was converted into its chloride by digesting it with an excess of ammonium chloride solution on the water-bath. The brown product was filtered, washed first with water, then with alcohol, and afterwards dried in air. The substance is practically insoluble in water. {Found: Ni, 9.08; N, 25.70; Cl, 10.86; H_2O (by loss at 110°), 8.29; $[Ni(C_{10}N_6H_{11}O)_2]Cl_2 \cdot 3H_2O$ requires Ni, 9.01; N, 25.78; Cl, 10.89; H_2O , 8.28 per cent}. [Found (for the dried product): Ni, 9.85; N, 28.16. Calc. Ni, 9.82; N, 28.10 per cent].

All attempts to prepare the corresponding complexes with trivalent cobalt and chromium ended in failures.

p-Phenylenedibiguanide Sulphate.—*p*-Phenylenediamine (10 g.), dicyandiamide (17 g.), 22 c.c. of 32% hydrochloric acid and 25 c.c. of water were heated under reflux for about 2 hours. To the cold mixture 100 c.c. of alcohol were added. The solution was then boiled with 5 g. of charcoal for a few minutes. The cold filtrate was then treated with 30 c.c. of dilute sulphuric acid (1:2 by volume). The crystals of the sulphate were filtered, washed first with cold water and then with alcohol and dried in air. (Found: N, 37.60; SO_4 , 25.71. $C_{10}N_{10}H_{16} \cdot 2H_2SO_4$ requires N, 37.43; SO_4 , 25.66 per cent).

Copper p-phenylenedibiguanidinium sulphate was obtained as a violet coloured powder by adding an ammoniacal solution of *p*-phenylenedibiguanide sulphate to an ammoniacal solution of copper sulphate. The product was filtered, washed and dried as usual. It is very sparingly soluble in water. {Found: Cu, 13.20; N, 28.89; SO_4 , 19.90; H_2O (by loss at 105°), 9.37. $[Cu(C_{10}N_{10}H_{16})]SO_4 \cdot 2.5H_2O$ requires Cu, 13.20; N, 29.10; SO_4 , 19.97; H_2O , 9.36 per cent}. Found (for the dried product): Cu, 14.54; N, 31.90. Calc. Cu, 14.47; N, 32.10 per cent.

The complex base was obtained from the above described complex sulphate when the latter, while still moist, was triturated with an excess of caustic soda solution in a mortar. The product was washed first with water till free from sulphate, then with alcohol, and finally dried in a desiccator over solid KOH.

It forms a pale violet powder, insoluble in cold water and organic solvents. The substance slowly absorbs CO_2 from air and liberates ammonia from solutions of ammonium salts. {Found: Cu, 12.88; N, 28.38; H_2O (by loss at 105°), 31.10. $[Cu(C_{10}N_{10}H_{11})]$, $8.5H_2O$ requires Cu, 12.94; N, 28.53; H_2O , 31.19 per cent}. [Found (for the dried product): Cu, 18.80; N, 41.10. Calc. Cu, 18.81; N, 41.48 per cent].

The complex chloride was obtained by digesting the complex base with ammonium chloride solution on the water-bath till the evolution of ammonia ceased. The product was filtered, washed and dried as usual.

The substance forms light violet powder, insoluble in cold water. {Found: Cu, 13.70; N, 29.83; Cl, 15.36; H_2O (by loss at 105°), 11.58. $[Cu(C_{10}N_{10}H_{11})]Cl \cdot 3H_2O$

requires Cu, 13.66; N, 30.01; Cl, 15.28, H₂O, 11.62 per cent}. [Found (for the dried product): Cu, 14.99; N, 34.20; Cl, 17.05. Calc. Cu, 15.07; N, 34.10; Cl, 17.10 per cent].

Nickel p-phenylenedibiguanidinium sulphate was obtained as a brick-red flocculent precipitate when an ammoniacal solution of *p*-phenylenedibiguanide sulphate was treated with that of nickel sulphate. This was washed and dried as usual. The substance is very sparingly soluble in hot water, but insoluble in alcohol. {Found: Ni, 12.50; N, 29.84; SO₄, 20.50; H₂O (by loss at 105°), 7.68. [Ni(C₁₀N₁₀H₁₂)]SO₄·2H₂O requires Ni, 12.57; N, 29.98; SO₄, 20.50; H₂O, 7.70 per cent}. [Found (for the dried substance): Ni, 13.58; N, 32.39; SO₄, 22.29. Calc. Ni, 13.62; N, 32.50; SO₄, 22.30 per cent].

The complex base was prepared by triturating the above described complex sulphate, while still moist, with an excess of caustic soda solution in a mortar. The dull red insoluble product was washed with water till free from sulphate and then dried over solid KOH in a desiccator. It gives alkaline reaction, absorbs CO₂ from air, and liberates ammonia from ammonium salt solutions. {Found: Ni, 14.87; N, 35.43; H₂O (by loss at 105°), 15.95. [Ni(C₁₀N₁₀H₁₄)]·3.5 H₂O requires Ni, 14.90; N, 35.55; H₂O, 15.92 per cent}. [Found (for the dried product): Ni, 17.60; N, 41.84. Calc. Ni, 17.53; N, 41.82 per cent].

The Complex Chloride.—The chloride of the complex base was obtained by digesting the base with an excess of ammonium chloride solution on the water-bath till the evolution of ammonia ceased. The insoluble, dull red product was filtered, washed and dried as usual. {Found: Ni, 12.66; N, 30.33; Cl, 15.40; H₂O (by loss at 110°), 11.70. [Ni(C₁₀N₁₀H₁₆)]Cl₂·3H₂O requires Ni, 12.76; N, 30.46; Cl, 15.40; H₂O, 11.74 per cent}. [Found (anhydrous product): Ni, 14.40; N, 33.59; Cl, 17.45. Calc. Ni, 14.46; N, 33.60; Cl, 17.50 per cent].

Chromium tris-p-Phenylenedibiguanide Base.—The complex chromium base was obtained as a rose-red precipitate by adding a solution of chrome alum to that of *p*-phenylenedibiguanide sulphate in caustic soda. The product was washed with ice-cold water till free from sulphate, then with alcohol, and afterwards dried over solid KOH in a desiccator. The substance is moderately soluble in water and reacts alkaline to litmus. It liberates ammonia from ammonium salt solutions. {Found: Cr, 10.15; N, 40.96; H₂O (by loss at 105°), 6.33. [Cr₂(C₁₀N₁₀H₁₄)₃].5H₂O requires Cr, 10.17; N, 41.09; H₂O, 8.85 per cent}. [Found (dried at 105°): Cr, 11.04; N, 44.32. [Cr₂(C₁₀N₁₀H₁₄)₃].1.5H₂O requires Cr, 11.03; N, 44.53 per cent}.

No salt of the complex chromium base could, however, be isolated. Similarly all attempts to prepare cobalt tris-*p*-phenylenedibiguanide complexes led to no fruitful results.

All the metallic complexes of *p*-acetylaminophenylbiguanide, as well as of *p*-phenylenedibiguanide, described here, decompose with boiling water. It therefore appears that substitution in the *para* position of the phenyl group in phenylbiguanide reduces the tendency to complex formation and the stability of the complex.

